

Kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions of iron(III) perchlorate with aldohexoses in presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl

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The kinetics of electron transfer reactions of iron(III) perchlorate with D-glucose, D-galactose and D-mannoses in presence of complexing 2,2'-bipyridyl have been studied under the pseudo-first order conditions. The results suggest the formation of 1 : 2 complex between Fe^{III} and 2,2'-bipyridyl. The complex reacts with aldohexose to form an intermediate complex which disproportionates in a slow step to form aldopentose by a free radical mechanism. A rate law has been derived.

In continuation of our studies on the electron transfer reactions of iron(III) perchlorate in presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl with aldopentoses and mannitol¹, we report here the results of kinetic and mechanistic studies of electron transfer reactions of present metal ion with aldohexoses (D-glucose, D-galactose and D-mannose).

Results and discussion

The first order kinetics in these reactions have been justified from the near constant values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) calculated by the usual procedure, re-

gression analysis and also by R/R method² in the typical kinetic runs. The k_{obs} varies with aldohexose and perchloric acid concentrations at constant Fe^{III} and bipyridyl concentrations (Table 1). The fractional values of log-log plots obtained in the aldohexoses concentration variations provide a kinetic evidence of complex formation between the active species of iron(III) and aldohexose molecule prior to rate determining step. The observed negative slope values (~-2.0) in perchloric acid variations were further confirmed by the observation of similar trends when hydrogen ion concentration was varied at constant perchlorate ion concentra-

Table 1. Variation of k_{obs} with aldohexose* and perchloric acid concentrations

$10^3[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2[\text{Bipy}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\lambda = 510 \text{ nm}$, Temp. = 318 K

$10^2[\text{Aldohexoses}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{obs} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			$10^3 k_o = k_{obs}/[\text{Aldohexose}]$		
		(A)	(B)	(C)	(A)	(B)	(C)
1.0	5.0	7.47	7.72	8.10	7.47	7.72	8.10
2.0	5.0	13.63	11.57	12.16	6.81	5.87	6.08
3.0	5.0	15.90	16.18	16.50	5.30	5.39	5.50
4.0	5.0	17.97	18.23	18.48	4.49	4.56	4.60
5.0	5.0	19.50	20.42	20.65	3.90	4.08	4.13
6.0	5.0	22.65	22.88	22.92	3.77	3.81	3.82
3.0	10.0	14.12	15.13	16.14	4.71	5.04	5.38
3.0	15.0	9.75	7.76	8.32	3.25	2.59	2.77
3.0	20.0	5.81	5.01	5.37	1.94	1.67	1.79
3.0	25.0	3.16	3.39	3.63	1.05	1.13	1.21

* (A) = D-Glucose, (B) = D-mannose, (C) = D-galactose.

Slopes of $\log k_{obs}$ and $\log [\text{Aldohexose}]$: 0.58 (A); 0.61 (B); 0.58 (C).

Slopes of k_{obs} and $\log [\text{HClO}_4]$: -1.60 (A); -1.62 (B); -1.62 (C).

Table 2. Variation of k_{obs} with hydrogen, perchlorate ions and bipyridyl concentrations*

$10^3[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2[\text{Aldohexoses}] = 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 318 K

$10^3[\text{H}^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{ClO}_4^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{Bipy}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\mu]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$		
				(A)	(B)	(C)
10.0	3.65	2.0	4.40	13.84	15.37	16.81
15.0	3.65	2.0	4.40	8.99	7.76	8.51
20.0	3.65	2.0	4.40	5.83	4.79	5.25
25.0	3.65	2.0	4.40	2.77	3.16	3.47
5.0	0.65	2.0	1.40	15.90	16.18	16.50
5.0	1.15	2.0	1.90	17.23	17.18	17.54
5.0	1.65	2.0	2.40	17.47	18.04	18.14
5.0	2.15	2.0	2.90	18.47	19.01	19.63
5.0	2.65	2.0	3.40	19.10	19.53	20.40
5.0	3.15	2.0	3.90	19.77	20.14	21.18
5.0	3.65	2.0	4.40	20.78	21.23	22.32
5.0	0.65	1.0	1.40	4.05	4.57	5.25
5.0	0.65	1.5	1.40	8.51	9.33	10.47
5.0	0.65	2.0	1.40	15.90	16.18	16.50
5.0	0.65	2.5	1.40	20.89	22.39	23.99
5.0	0.65	3.0	1.40	30.33	30.57	32.25

*(A) = D-Glucose, (B) = D-mannose, (C) = D-galactose.

Slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ and $\log [\text{H}^+]$: -1.67 (A); -1.81 (B); -1.72 (C).

Slopes of k_{obs} and $\log [\text{Bipy}]$: 1.83 (A); 1.74 (B); 1.65 (C).

Slopes of k_{obs} and $\log [\mu]^{1/2}$: 0.12 (A); 0.12 (B); 0.14 (C)

Table 3. Activation parameters*

$10^3[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2[\text{Aldohexoses}] = 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2[\text{Bipy}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. K	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$			$\Delta H^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$			$-\Delta S^\ddagger (\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1})$		
	(A)	(B)	(C)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(A)	(B)	(C)
298	4.02	4.04	4.65	47.35	45.77	43.64	74.54	79.78	85.76
303	7.76	6.02	6.76	46.50	45.53	43.43	74.71	79.92	85.90
308	10.72	8.10	9.25	46.41	45.53	43.34	74.84	80.05	86.04
313	11.92	10.96	13.49	46.89	45.48	43.06	74.98	80.19	86.17
318	15.90	16.18	16.50	46.88	45.14	43.22	75.11	80.32	86.30
	Average			46.81	45.49	43.34	74.84	80.05	86.05
				±	±	±	±	±	±
				0.30	0.14	0.16	0.17	0.16	0.16

*(A) = D-Glucose, (B) = D-mannose, (C) = D-galactose.

tion (Table 2). Increase in k_{obs} with perchlorate ion (ionic strength) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (Table 2) indicates the involvement of positively charged active species of iron(III)-bipyridyl complex in these reactions. The activation parameters computed from the rate data obtained at different temperatures are given in Table 3.

The formation of reactive species³ of iron(III) in pres-

ence of complexing protonated pyridyl ion⁴ can be shown as in eqn. (1). However, the small probability of the formation of dimeric and/or hydrolyzed form of iron(III) can not be ruled out,

The aldohexose molecule then reacts with the reactive species of iron(III) predominantly through its free aldehydo form to an intermediate complex which then disproportionates in slow rate-determining step to produce a carbon centred free radical (eqn. 2), confirmed by induced polymerization reaction with acryl nitrile,

The formation of aldohexose-derived free radicals in these reactions is consistent with the results obtained during the photo and thermal electron transfer reactions of reducing sugars with metal ions studied by ESR technique of spin-trapping⁵. The free radical formed (eqn. 2) is further oxidized by iron(III) to the respective aldopentose in a fast step (eqn. 3).

The proposed common mechanism and the observed 2 : 1 stoichiometry of Fe^{III} and aldohexose for all the three aldohexoses (isokinetic temp. 311 K) under the kinetic run conditions are supported by paper chromatographic identification of the products and also by quantitative estimation of formic acid.

However, in the presence of large excess Fe^{III} concentrations, the initial reaction products (aldopentoses) are further oxidized to formic acid, confirmed by paper chromatography. The stoichiometric equation under these conditions when Fe^{III} is in large excess can be proposed from the experimental 12 : 1 stoichiometry of Fe^{III} and aldohexose as in eqn. (4),

On the basis of these mechanistic steps (eqns. 1–3), the rate law for these reactions can be derived as in eqn. (5),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} &= \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{BipyH}^+]^2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{BipyH}^+]^2 + K_1K_2[\text{BipyH}^+]^2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6]} \\ &= k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The validation of rate law (eqn. 5) has been done from the rearranged form of rate law as in eqn. (6),

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{kK_1K_2[\text{BipyH}^+]^2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (6)$$

Linear plots with positive intercepts were obtained between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6] \cdot [\text{H}^+]^2$ and $1/[\text{BipyH}^+]^2$ using the rate data of Tables 1 and 2. Thus the proposed mechanistic steps (eqns. 1–3) and the derived rate law (eqns. 5 and 6) explain the results of this study.

Experimental

Kinetics of these electron transfer reactions was monitored by the change in absorbance with time of the product $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Bipy})_2]^{2+}$ (eqn. 2) at 510 nm in presence of excess concentrations of aldohexose, perchloric acid and 2,2'-bipyridyl at constant temperature ($\pm 1.0^\circ$). In all these kinetic experiments, duplicate rate measurements were reproducible within $\sim 1\%$. The other experimental details are the same as described elsewhere⁶.

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